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Co-designing a new engineering curriculum with industry

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ABSTRACT

Global changes in technology and culture have drastically altered the needs of industry and society and thus the graduate engineering workforce required to fulfil those needs. With access to the whole body of human knowledge at the touch of a fingertip, learning is moving away from merely accumulating a body of facts. Instead, future engineering graduates need skills in assimilating and applying knowledge, thinking creatively, working collaboratively and in being agile and embracing change. As the mind-sets, skill-sets and knowledge-sets needed by engineering graduates shift, so too must higher education curricula, shifting to an experience-based curriculum that stimulates students to develop personal qualities and professional skills alongside the specialist knowledge of their field. Authentic, relevant student experiences that give engineering students employable skills cannot be created in isolation in universities thus a new curriculum is needed, to be co-designed with employers, industry experts, professional bodies and education specialists. This paper describes efforts underway to develop a new engineering curriculum with industry-led and project-based learning experiences running throughout the course and will propose a model for the co-design of this curriculum with industry and other key stakeholders.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, University-Business cooperation, Skills and Engineering Education

Keywords: Curriculum, Work-integrated learning, Industry, Project-based learning

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INTRODUCTION

Global changes in technology and culture have drastically altered the requirements of industry and society and thus the graduate engineering workforce required to fulfil those needs. With access to the whole body of human knowledge at the touch of a fingertip, learning is moving away from merely accumulating a body of facts. Instead, future engineering graduates need skills in assimilating and applying knowledge, in thinking creatively and collaboratively, in being agile and embracing change in a rapidly transforming world. Many studies and reports have called for a new approach to engineering education (e.g. Beanland and Hadgraft [1] and King [2]), indicating that different types of engineers are needed in 21st century engineering practice. Being able to synthesise information to solve problems and create solutions has become far more important than the ability to remember facts. The ability to understand diverse consumer needs and communicate in many ways with diverse stakeholders is key to working in a global market.

Research in engineering education has seen some changing trends with the increased application of project-based learning, team work, flipped classrooms, use of open online resources, and more authentic assessment practices. Work-integrated learning opportunities, along with study tours and service learning projects, are also becoming more widely valued. However, many changes are incremental and often project and team work, study tours or placements are either optional extras or bolt-ons that are experienced once by the student but not integrated into the curriculum of the wider degree program.

Though most, if not all, accreditation bodies include professional skills as a crucial part of their accreditation processes [3-5], there has been a conflict between the growing awareness that engineers need to possess a wide array of personal and professional skills and the perceived need to cover in depth all of the increasing technical content [6]. Professional skills such as communication, teamwork and ethics are also often perceived as difficult to teach and assess, though there are many examples of how these skills can be taught if explicitly targeted (see Shuman, Besterfield-Sacre [7] for a comprehensive overview).

A recent report by the Australian Council of Engineering Deans made a series of six recommendations to ensure engineering schools can meet the country's future need for engineers, one of which was for "educators and industry practitioners to engage more intensively to strengthen the authenticity of engineering students' education" with "more effective and increasing input from industry practitioners to engineering schools in the processes of setting, reviewing and tracking attainment of graduate outcomes" [2]. Authentic and relevant student experiences that develop professional skills in engineering students cannot be created in isolation in universities. For true work-integrated learning a new curriculum is needed, including experiences that must be co-designed with employers, industry experts, professional bodies and education specialists. Engineering practitioners and employers are best placed to identify the tasks that engineering graduates will be faced with and the knowledge-sets, skill-sets and mind-sets they need to accomplish those tasks.

This paper outlines a framework for co-designing a new engineering curriculum with industry, moving away from a content-driven curriculum and towards an approach aimed at developing professional skill-sets and mind-sets. Though this work is undertaken in an engineering context within Swinburne University's Engineering Practice Academy, it is with the aim that the consultative curriculum co-design process will be applicable to other discipline areas in higher education.

THE CONSULTATIVE CURRICULUM DESIGN PROCESS

1.1 Overview

An overview of the curriculum design process is presented in Figure 1. The curriculum co-design requires input from a range of stakeholders which is fed into an iterative development process under the overarching goal of developing graduates with skills allowing them to work as the engineers of the future. The proposed course requires an experience-based rather than a content-focused curriculum with the objective that the engineers graduating from the course must be employable. Employability is defined by Yorke [8] as having “skills, understandings and personal attributes – that makes graduates more likely to gain employment and be successful in their chosen occupations, which benefits themselves, the workforce, the community and the economy.”

Fig. 1. Framework for consultative curriculum co-design

The structure was adapted from the “Design your Discipline (DYD)” stakeholder consultation process [9] which was created to facilitate curriculum renewal in undergraduate programs. In the DYD process consultation takes three forms: “stakeholder consultation” to gather a full range of views from diverse stakeholders, “consensus building” to come to an agreed position and “engagement for change” to engage stakeholders in future change processes. Engagement for change is particularly important in this case as the industry partners being consulted are also being sought as partners in the delivery and assessment of the future course and their input will ideally be ongoing. The aim of engaging industry partners in the creation of the curriculum at all stages is both to benefit from their expertise and give them a sense of ownership of the program being developed.

Current engineering students have also been consulted as part of the process and it is the intention to involve future cohorts of students in the shaping of the curriculum and other aspects of the course. 'Students as partners' is a growing field of study in the education community and has emerged from international acknowledgement that new approaches are needed to engage students in their learning [10]. The UK Higher Education Academy (HEA) has published a framework for engaging students as partners based on dozens of documented case studies, one outcome of which is the advocacy of student partnership in curriculum design and pedagogic consultancy [11]. This paper however focuses on consultation with industry; forthcoming papers will describe the consultation process with students.

Close consultation with relevant professional bodies is also necessary. Engineering Australia (EA), as the professional body responsible for accrediting engineering programs, was consulted. The EA Stage 1 competency standards for Professional Engineers (the competencies deemed necessary for entry to practice corresponding to an accredited 4-year Bachelor or 5-year Masters degree) were used as a guiding input to the curriculum design. The specific university course objectives and graduate attributes for current engineering courses, which were developed from and closely linked to the EA competencies, were also used alongside broader university-wide values and goals.

1.2 Ideas Workshops

Potential partners were identified by the University collaborations and partnerships team, leveraging existing research connections and seeking new partnerships. The aim was to connect with a range of partners spanning as broad a range of organisations as possible spanning, for example defence, mining, not-for-profits, spanning small local businesses to large multinational corporations. Sixty-six individuals from fifty organisations participated in three workshops, split between on-campus and external venues, and morning and afternoon time slots, so participation was not limited by geography or scheduling.

The workshops included a presentation about the vision of the project but the main focus was not on telling the participants what was being planned, but asking them for their input. The key messages were that anything was possible and that genuine collaboration was integral to the whole enterprise.

The bulk of the workshop consisted of three micro-sessions where questions were posed and discussed by the industry participants in mixed groupings, consisting of participants representing diverse industries to encourage varied viewpoints. Notes were taken by project members and groups fed back to the wider workshop, with common themes emerging, but some groups providing unique insights.

The themes of the micro-sessions were:

- Emerging industries and industry trends
- Skill-sets and mind-sets required of graduates
- Tasks performed by graduates

The notes were then transcribed and coded to identify key themes and the frequency with which they were mentioned. Many of the themes occurred across all the micro-session discussions, for example "interdisciplinarity" and "working globally". The data on emerging industries and trends was used to inform the creation of new specialisms and aspects of the discipline-specific curriculum and are not discussed further in this paper. The data on the professional skills and personal traits required by engineers

were used to inform the next stage of the curriculum design process. A summary of the outcomes of the workshops was also circulated to all industry participants.

1.3 Analysis and framing

Information about the skills required of the engineering graduates of the future gathered from the ideas workshops was combined and compared with Engineers Australia's Stage 1 Competencies and the university's own stated Engineering Competencies as well as considering more general competencies such as Lominger's 67 competencies to measure a person's effectiveness in business [12].

These were grouped by the authors who debated the structure and links between the skills and organised them into common themes. Innovative curriculum and learning models (e.g. Thinking Like and Engineer [13] and Vitae [14]) and other conceptual frameworks for categorising competencies such as constellations and multidimensional representations [15] were used as examples of how to organise and structure skills into a curriculum framework. Once a curriculum framework was agreed on, the skills and competencies identified from the ideas workshops and other sources were mapped to the framework to form a draft curriculum.

1.4 Curriculum development workshops

A total of 21 participants from 18 organisations took part in the second set of workshops. Most participants had been involved in the ideas workshops but 6 were new participants. The format was similar to the previous workshops, with the initial presentation explaining the current curriculum draft and the facilitated group work involving discussion around the draft with feedback presented by group members. The questions industry participants were asked to focus on were:

- Sense check/ communicative validity – the new skills curriculum is very different from traditional content focused curriculum. Does it make sense?
- Are there any skills missing or requiring more emphasis?
- How could this framework be used to describe graduates given it is very different from a transcript listing grades and subject areas?

The draft curriculum was updated after the first workshop and the second draft dissected by participants during the second workshop. The process of co-designing a curriculum with industry partners is necessarily iterative and can be repeated as many times as needed until the additions to the curriculum are negligible. Individual consultations with industry partners on specific aspects are also useful at this stage, to further break down particular curriculum points.

1.5 Draft curriculum

The draft curriculum is presented in figure 2. It consists of four domains, each of which is divided into three sub-domains.

Fig. 2. The domains and sub-domains of the draft curriculum.

2 REFLECTION

Industrial partner buy-in and enthusiasm are key, and so far have been extremely high. From the very first ideas workshops, industry participants were using language such as “we” when discussing the creation of the new course and in later workshops participants discussed having actively promoted the new curriculum ideas in their organisations and with external clients.

The draft curriculum, with a much greater focus on professional skills and personal attributes than in traditional programs, seems to have resonated with workshop participants, with for example one industry partner summarising this as “I hire a person, not a position”. This is consistent with results from the literature where attitudinal and non-technical competencies have been rated as just as if not more important than technical knowledge [16].

The areas of the curriculum that industry partners particularly contributed to in the curriculum development stage were around business and enterprise and the knowledge and skills graduates would need in this area. They also contributed to expanding on the self-management, career literacy and creativity skills that graduates would require. In areas such as communication and disciplinary knowledge the model was validated but not much expanded upon after the initial ideas workshop.

There are several areas for further study that have emerged from the curriculum design workshops. One repeated theme in the early ideas workshops was that of “the fundamentals”, with industry participants adamant that these still be taught without a clear explanation of what this meant, and without clarity as to whether participants from different industry sectors all considered the fundamentals to be the same knowledge set. This requires further investigation as to what fundamental maths, science, or other engineering knowledge is required by modern engineers, as opposed to what is expected to be taught based on an adherence to what has been taught in the past.

Another area of investigation is how to present the outcomes of this curriculum model in a form that can be understood by employers in the manner of a transcript. This is an important concern as a key goal of this new degree is to increase employability, and any improvements in graduate skills are moot if these skills cannot be communicated clearly to potential employers. More than just listing the competencies graduates will have demonstrated, there will also need to be a way to differentiate between students and elucidate in which curriculum areas they have developed specific depth.

An interesting aspect of this process of co-designing a curriculum with industry participation is how quickly ideas and language develop. Initial curriculum discussions among the academics were based around a skills triad of knowledge sets, skill-sets and mind-sets. After the ideas workshops it rapidly became apparent that four categories were required, with skill sets subdividing into business & enterprise skills and communication & interpersonal skills, each of which were deemed sufficiently crucial and broad in terms of sub-themes to warrant separate consideration. The language also evolved, for example from initially talking about 'mind-sets' during the consultation process to subsequently using terminology such as 'self' and 'personal attributes'. This continual development of language and ways of thinking is a sign that the co-design is more than a token consultation, but is a true co-construction of ideas.

Another interesting aspect of the process is how it can be applied in many areas beyond engineering. This is both in terms of the transferability of this framework to other disciplines, indeed it is designed to become part of a wider university strategy, but also in terms of the curriculum developed. The curriculum, while containing some aspects unique to engineering practice, is primarily comprised of competencies that apply to many if not all fields of study in higher education.

3 CONCLUSION

A rapidly changing world requires engineers with different skills sets and thus radically different engineering degrees to prepare them for the workplace. This paper has proposed a framework for co-designing the curriculum for such a degree with industry partners, ensuring its relevance in the workplace and the employability of graduates from such a program. The process has been embraced by industry partners who have contributed enthusiastically to the initial ideas workshops and by providing insights into subsequent draft versions of the curriculum. The process is ongoing, both in terms of the academic-industry collaboration in developing the curriculum but also beyond into industry partners being involved in the setting, delivery and assessment of student projects. Future work will involve establishing frameworks for this continued collaboration as well as expanding on aspects of the curriculum such as "fundamental knowledge" and investigating how such a revolutionary curriculum can be presented to potential employers in terms of explaining graduate capabilities. Overall, the process of co-designing the curriculum has been one of true collaboration that has been positively received by industry partners and is the first step in creating an engineering degree with high levels of industry engagement leading to highly employable graduates.

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